

1,6-Bis-(arylsulphoxido)-2,4-hexadiyne (IV) : To a stirring solution of 1,6-bis-(arylthio)-2,4-hexadiyne (0.001 M) in methylene chloride (10 ml) at 0-5°, MCPBA (0.002 M) in methylene chloride (15 ml) was added dropwise over 30 min and stirring at this temperature (0-5°) was continued for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was washed with Na₂CO₃ solution (5%), saturated salt water and water successively and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. The solvent was removed to give a mixture of two products as indicated by tlc. These were separated by column chromatography (silica gel) to give IV 78-81% and V 8-12%. The product (IV) was recrystallised from chloroform-acetone mixture. Yield of IVa 80%, m.p. 140°; IVb 78%, m.p. 162°; IVc 81%, m.p. 136°, PMR (CDCl₃) in δ (400 MHz) : IVa 2.45(s, 6H), 3.60-3.76 (q, 4H), 7.32-7.60(m, 8H); IVb 3.15-3.42(q, 4H), 6.90-7.10(m, 8H); IVc 3.62-3.82(q, 4H), 7.56-7.75(m, 10H). IVa gave molecular ion peak (m/e) at 354. Elemental analysis (C, H) : IVa Found : C, 67.63; H, 5.17. Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₈S₂O₂; C, 67.79; H, 5.12%; IVb Found : C, 54.90; H, 3.18. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₄S₂Cl₂O₂; C, 54.68; H, 3.03%; IVc Found : C, 66.20; H, 4.17. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₄S₂O₂; C, 66.25; H, 4.29%.

1-Arylsulphoxido-6-arylsulphonyl hexa-2,4-diyne (V) : To a stirring solution of 1,6-bis-(arylthio)-2,4-hexadiyne (0.001 M) in methylene chloride (10 ml) at 0-5°, MCPBA (0.003 M) in methylene chloride (15 ml) was added dropwise over 30 min and stirring was continued for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was then washed by Na₂CO₃ solution (5%), saturated salt water and finally with water, dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. Solvent was removed to give a mixture of three products as shown by tlc. These were separated by column chromatography (silica gel) to give IV 5-10%, V 40-65% and VI 8-20%. The compound (V) was recrystallised from chloroform-acetone mixture. The yield of Va 60%, m.p. 142°; Vb 40%, m.p. 145°; Vc 65%, m.p. 139°. PMR (CDCl₃) in δ : Va (400 MHz) 2.40-2.50(d, 6H), 3.62-3.74(q, 2H), 4.00(s, 2H), 7.32-7.84(m, 8H); Vc (200 MHz) 3.70 (s, 2H), 4.04(s, 2H), 7.58-8.00(m, 10H). Va gave molecular ion peak (m/e) at 370. Elemental analysis (C, H) : Va Found : C, 64.64; H, 4.35. Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₈S₂O₃; C, 64.86; H, 4.86%.

1,6-Bis-(arylsulphonyl)-2,4-hexadiyne (VI) : To a stirring solution of 1,6-bis-(arylthio)-2,4-hexadiyne (0.001 M) in methylene chloride (10 ml) at 0-5°, MCPBA (0.004 M) in methylene chloride (20 ml) was added dropwise over 20 min and stirring continued at r.t. for 2 hr. VI was then obtained as white solid from this reaction mixture following the work up procedure of compound V. These were recrystallised from chloroform-acetone mixture. The yield of VIa 87%, m.p. 210°; VIb 90%, m.p. 206°; VIc 90%, m.p. 190°. PMR (CDCl₃) in δ : VIa (400 MHz) 2.44 (s, 6H), 4.78 (s, 4H), 7.46-7.82 (m, 8H); VIb (90 MHz) 4.00 (s, 4H), 7.25-7.95 (m, 8H); VIc (90 MHz) 3.90 (s, 4H), 7.45-7.90 (m, 10H). VIa gave molecular ion peak (m/e) at 386. Elemental analysis (C, H) : VIa Found : C, 62.02; H, 4.80. Calcd. for

C₂₀H₁₈S₂O₄; C, 62.17; H, 4.70%; VIb Found : C, 50.42; H, 2.65. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₄S₂Cl₂O₄; C, 50.58; H, 2.81%; VIc Found : C, 60.55; H, 3.67. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₄S₂O₄; C, 60.33; H, 3.91%.

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Bromomethylation Studies in Flavone and Flavanone Derivatives

H. N. JHA

Department of Chemistry, MMH College, Ghaziabad-201 001 and

V. S. PARMAR and MOHAN KATYAL*

St. Stephen's College, Delhi-110 007

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IN view of the occurrence of several C-methylated flavonoids in nature, it is important to adopt synthetic methodology for the introduction of methyl group in the aromatic ring. One method to prepare the C-methyl compounds is the reductive dehalogenation of the corresponding halomethyl (chloro- or bromo-) derivatives. The preparations of chloromethyl derivatives of chromones, flavones and 7-methoxyflavanone have been reported earlier¹⁻⁴. No work on bromomethylation of these groups of compounds appears to have been published earlier. The present communication describes the bromomethylation of flavones and

flavanones using hydrobromic acid gas and paraformaldehyde suspended in glacial acetic acid with or without catalyst.

Results and Discussion

7-Hydroxyflavone with paraformaldehyde and hydrogen bromide gas gave monobromomethyl derivative (m.p. 226-28°, yield 44%) which was shown to be 7-hydroxy-8-bromomethylflavone, as on reaction with zinc and acetic acid it gave the known 7-hydroxy-8-methylflavone, m.p. 253-54° (lit.⁵ m.p. 255-57°). Similarly, 6-hydroxyflavone on bromomethylation gave the 5-bromomethyl-6-hydroxyflavone (m.p. 238-39°, yield 53%, and the latter on treatment with hexamine and glacial acetic acid gave the known 6-hydroxy-5-formylflavone, m.p. 219-20° (lit.⁶ m.p. 220-22°). 7-Methoxyflavone on bromomethylation afforded its 8-bromomethyl derivative (m.p. 234-36°, yield 62%) which on treatment with Zn/AcOH gave the known 8-methyl-7-methoxyflavone, m.p. 174-76° (lit.³ m.p. 175-76°). No di- or tribromomethyl derivative could be prepared even with excess of paraformaldehyde and zinc chloride as a catalyst.

Matsuoka² chloromethylated flavanone but could not assign any definite structure to the chloromethyl derivative. Flavanone on bromomethylation afforded 3-bromomethylflavanone (m.p. 156-57°, yield 42%) which on reaction with Zn/AcOH and dehydrogenation with selenium dioxide gave 3-methylflavone, m.p. 71-72° (lit.⁷ m.p. 72-74°). When 7-methoxyflavanone was bromomethylated under these conditions, it formed its 8-bromomethyl derivative (m.p. 159-61°, yield 35%) which on debromination and dehydrogenation gave 7-methoxy-8-methylflavone, m.p. 174-75° (lit.⁸ m.p. 175-76°).

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. The comparisons with authentic samples were made by co-tlc, co-ir and mixed m.p. The reductive dehalogenation with zinc and acetic acid and formylation with hexamine were carried out by the well known standard methods^{4,6}. The bromomethylation of the compounds was done following the general method given below for hydroxyflavanone.

To a solution of hydroxyflavone (2 g) in glacial acetic acid (70 ml) paraformaldehyde (3.5 g) was added. The temp. was maintained at 80-90° on a water bath and a continuous stream of dry hydrogen bromide gas was passed for 4 hr when a shining yellow crystalline product separated out. The reaction mixture on cooling deposited more of this solid which crystallized from benzene-petroleum ether mixture.

All these compounds analysed correctly for C, H and Br.

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